

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

	Include	Exclude
Study design	Primary research studies (cohort, cross-sectional, case series (more than 10 patients). Include scoping and systematic reviews at secondary screening to screen included primary studies	Opinion, narratives, case study, letters to editor, laboratory studies
Topic	Climate change impacts	Climate change adaptation or resilience
Population	Human studies	Animal studies, plant/crop/grass studies
Exposure	<p>Extreme weather due to climate change:</p> <p><u>Extreme temperatures</u>: cold, heat, severe winter conditions such as snow/ice or frost/freeze.</p> <p><u>Storm</u>: extra-tropical storms, tropical storms, convective storms – includes derecho, hail, lightning/thunderstorm, rain, tornado, sand/dust storm, storm/surge, wind, cyclone, typhoon</p> <p><u>Flood</u>: coastal flood, riverine flood, flash flood, ice jam flood</p> <p><u>Avalanche</u>: snow debris, mudflow</p> <p><u>Drought</u></p> <p><u>Wildfire</u>: forest fire, land fire, brush fire, bush fire, pasture fires</p>	<p>Extreme events that are not climate related:</p> <p><u>Earthquake</u>: ground movement, tsunami</p> <p><u>Dry mass movement</u>: rockfall, landslide</p> <p><u>Volcanic activity</u>: ash fall, lahar, pyroclastic flow, lava flow</p> <p><u>Epidemic</u>: viral, bacterial, parasitic, fungal, prion</p> <p><u>Insect infestation</u>: grasshopper, locust</p> <p><u>Animal accident</u></p> <p><u>Space weather</u>: geomagnetic storm</p> <p><u>Human-made disasters</u>: chemical spill, explosion, gas leak</p>
Measure of mental health impact	<p>Any: ICD codes</p> <p>Symptom scales, Screening tools</p> <p>Administrative data: hospital admissions, mortality, ER visits</p>	
Outcome	Mental health disorders (anxiety, depression, PTSD, acute stress, suicidal behaviour, intentional self-harm, mood disorder, dementia, Alzheimer disease, schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders, acute and transient psychotic disorders, psychosis, substance use and addiction)	Domestic abuse, general climate change anxiety, psychological and behavioural disorders associated with sexual development and orientation, disorders of psychological development